

HOW TO INCREASE STUDENTS' MOTIVATION IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract: The article highlights the essence of the concept of “motivation” in language learning and identifies the ways to increase students’ motivation to learn English. To achieve this goal, we consider active teaching methods, group work in the classroom, as well as extensive use of ICT technologies.

Keywords: motivation, learning a foreign language, teaching methods, tasks

Аннотация: В статье освещается сущность понятия «мотивация» в изучении языка и определяются пути повышения мотивации учащихся к изучению английского языка. Для достижения этой цели мы рассматриваем активные методы обучения, групповую работу на уроке, а также широкое использование ИКТ-технологий.

Ключевые слова: мотивация, изучение иностранного языка, методы обучения, задания.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada chet tili o'rganishda “motivatsiya” tushunchasining mohiyati va talabalarning ingliz tilini o'rganishga bolgan motivatsiyasini oshirish yo'llari yoritilgan. Maqsadni amalga oshirish uchun biz o'qitishning faol usullarini, darsda guruhlarda ishlash, va shuningdek, AKT texnologiyalaridan keng foydalanishni ko'rib chiqamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: motivatsiya, chet tilini o'rganish, o'qitish usullari, topshiriqlar.

Analysis of recent studies and publications highlight possible ways to increase the motivation of students to study English. First, let us define the essence of the concept of “motivation” in the context of our study. In modern psychology, motivation is seen as a complex "triggering mechanism" of human life, whether it be work, behavior, cognition and communication. Psychologists define motivation as a specific motive, both as a single system of motives, and as a special area that includes needs, motives, goals, interests in their complex interweaving and interaction. Objects of the external world, representations, ideas, feelings and experiences can act as a motive. In other words, motivation is the most important spring in the process of mastering a foreign language, ensuring its effectiveness; one must keep in mind the following: motivation is a side of the subjective world of the student; it is determined by his own motives and predilections, perceived by him needs. Hence all the difficulties of calling motivation from the outside. The teacher can only indirectly influence it,

creating the prerequisites and forming the foundations on the basis of which the students have a personal interest in the work.

In a broad sense, two types of motivation are distinguished: external and internal. Extrinsic motivation exists in two varieties: broad social motivation and narrow personal motivation. In relation to a foreign language, broad social motivation is manifested in the desire of students to master a foreign language, cultural values with the prospect of using it in various situations of interpersonal and intercultural interaction and identifying themselves with a certain group of native speakers. Narrow motivation determines the attitude to mastering a foreign language as a way of self-affirmation, achievement of success and self-development.

Motivation can be interpreted as a source of human activity, as a system of motivating forces for any activity and behavior. Motivation is considered as a system of factors influencing human behavior (this includes needs, motives, goals, intentions, aspirations, and much more), and as a characteristic of a process that stimulates and maintains a person's activity at a certain level.

We identified students' motivation by conducting a survey among 1st-2nd year students studying English language as a specialty. Results showed that students are more interested in doing tasks related to their future profession and want to be good future English teachers.

In the context of our issue, we think the process of teaching English must meet the following requirements: focus on the personality of the student; taking into account his/her individual characteristics; the creation of tasks in the learning process; promote personal and professional development; providing conditions for the active work of each student and the involvement of students in joint activities; communicative orientation;

In accordance with the requirements of modern didactics, the pedagogical process must be built on the principles of a student-centered approach. For example, the teacher should inform students about the objectives of the lesson, and the tasks should be associated with mastering speech activities.

The next organizational point that contributes to increasing the motivation of students is the use of group work in the English class. Various forms of team work allow differentiating educational activities, providing conditions for involving students in joint activities, taking into account the individual characteristics and preferences of students, which contributes to the intensification of educational work, gives it emotional appeal and also plays a role in the formation of appropriate motivation. Each student can perform a

feasible part of the overall task, which will also play an important role in the development of positive motivation.

We use active methods of teaching a foreign language at a university, which encourage students to be active in thought and practice in the process of mastering educational material. These methods have a multi-purpose focus: they contribute to the improvement of language training and personal and professional development of students, provide an active nature of the assimilation of knowledge and skills, and provide an opportunity for active interpersonal interaction. Active learning methods are designed to intensify the learning process, make it more productive, as well as form and further develop the motivation for learning. The most popular and widely used in the process of teaching a foreign language are projects, role-playing, games, discussions, oral and written presentations and case studies.

However, the teacher must understand that communication in a foreign language will not start on its own, that it is not enough just to divide students into pairs or groups. It is necessary to create motives for this communication by offering an exciting task, to create a learning-problem (conflict) situation, which will be an incentive for communication in a small group.

Besides, we can use teaching aids such as ICT tools, multimedia technologies, and internet technologies, electronic educational resources that provide us with a number of advantages over traditional teaching aids and have the greatest motivating effect in the process of teaching a foreign language. The active introduction of new information technologies and electronic network learning (e-learning) on technological platforms - learning management systems (LMS) in the learning process through the use of interactive tasks, computer and multimedia technologies, undoubtedly, helps to increase motivation and improve the process formation of foreign language skills and abilities of students.

In short, it is crucial to mention that we can a variety of teaching methods, select language materials due to level of complexity, interests of students, creating a friendly atmosphere in the classroom, will really increase motivation to support the interest of students in learning English.

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